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Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Definition
BBI JU	Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking
BCT	Blockchain technology
CBE JU	Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	Europe
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, & Resuable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse gas emissions
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
M	month
MS	Microsoft
PCO	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
T	Task
TL	Task Leader

Executive Summary

This document deals with the research data **produced, collected and preserved** during the project, as well as with the way that those data will be **handled after the end of the project**.

It has to be clarified that this Data Management Plan (DMP) is not a fixed document but evolves during the lifespan of the project. Indeed, this is the **second revision of the original version submitted in M6**. Another revision is scheduled on M36.

Being TRUSTyFOOD a CSA, the majority of the results born as public, even if a preliminary analysis on any Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) needs to be done before releasing the document. The TRUSTyFOOD project abides by the European Commission's vision that information already paid for through EC funding should not be paid for again each time it is accessed or used by the research community and that it should benefit European companies and citizens to the full. This means making publicly-funded scientific information available online, at no extra cost, to European researchers, innovative industries and citizens, while ensuring long-term preservation.

1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires the establishment and regular update of a Data Management Plan since it is not a static document but rather evolves over the project's lifespan. Accordingly, TRUSTyFOOD planned three related deliverables respectively at months 6, 18 and 36.

This document represents the update of the DMP (v1), submitted in M6. Following the same template recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, with this DMP (v2), data have been updated/revised where changes raised. The rest of the document is maintained mostly unchanged, as it is still valid.

1.2. Guiding principles: general purpose for re-using or generating open publicly-funded scientific data

The TRUSTyFOOD project abides by the European Commission's vision¹ that “*fuller and wider access to scientific publications and data will help to:*

- *accelerate innovation (faster to market = faster growth);*
- *foster collaboration and avoid duplication of effort (greater efficiency);*
- *build on previous research results (improved quality of results);*
- *involve citizens and society (improved transparency of the scientific process).*

Indeed, “*what is at stake is the speed of scientific progress and the return on R&D investment, and in particular publicly-funded investment which has enormous potential for boosting productivity, competitiveness and growth. Improving access to scientific information is also about increasing openness and transparency, which are essential features of responsible research and innovation, and it contributes to better policy-making in a variety of areas. To ensure economic growth and to address the societal challenges of the 21st century, it is essential to optimise the circulation and transfer of scientific knowledge among key stakeholders in European research — universities, funding bodies, libraries, innovative enterprises, governments and policy-makers, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and society at large*”.

“*The vision underlying the Commission's strategy on open data and knowledge circulation is that information already paid for by the public purse should not be paid for again each time it is accessed or used, and that it should benefit European companies and citizens to the full. This means making publicly-funded scientific information available online, at no extra cost, to European researchers and citizens via sustainable e-infrastructures, also ensuring long-term access to avoid losing scientific information of unique value*”.

1.3. Data Management Plan: general purpose

The DMP provides an easy overview of research **data** the project is expected **to generate**, the types and **formats** of this data, and **how** this data is **processed and stored** to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The DMP can reflect the FAIR framework by accounting for its principles and expressing them via the use of tools.

¹ European Commission (2012). Towards better access to scientific information: Boosting the benefits of public investments in research. [Source](#).

The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to **good data handling** during the project's lifetime, and to describe how such data will be curated and preserved.

This data can either be made publicly available or not according to the Grant Agreement and to the need of the partners to preserve ethical or IPR rules and related benefits derived from project results and activities.

Essentially, the Data Management Plan will answer the following main questions:

- What types of data will the **project re-use** and what will you re-use it for?
- What types of data will the project **generate**?
- What data is to be **shared** for the benefit of the scientific **community**?
- What data **cannot** be made **available**? Why?
- What **format** will the shared data have?
- **How** will this data be exploited and/or shared/**made accessible** for verification and re-use?
- **How** will this data be curated and **preserved**?

1.4. Specific purpose of the data generation or re-use in relation to the objectives of the project

TRUSTyFOOD is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) and - as such - it is born with a strategic and policy-oriented spirit. Accordingly, most of the data collected and generated has the only purpose of being shared outside. **An important role is attributed to the communication and dissemination Work Package (WP), which will convey the results as they are generated towards the target audience.**

TRUSTyFOOD has been funded to clarify the current context of blockchain applications in the agri-food sector and alleviate the confusion around the technology. The intention is to provide evidences and recommendations useful to make informed choices, both at policies level and by end users.

1.5. Basic issues that will be dealt with for the data management

The following are fundamental issues that will be addressed for the data that can be shared:

- **Dataset reference and name**
The identifier for the datasets to be produced will have the following format: TRUSTyFOOD_[descriptive name/related paper name]_[date of production of the data]_version
- **Dataset description**
Description of the data will include:
 - Its origin, nature, scale and to whom it could be useful, and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and re-use.
 - Its format
 - Tools required for data utilisation (for example specialised software)
 - Accessory information

- **Standards and metadata**
Reference to any related standards (if any). If these do not exist, an outline of how and what metadata will be created, if needed.
- **Data sharing**
Description of how data will be shared, including access procedures, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and the definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating in particular the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.). In case the dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g. ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related).
- **Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup) and access modality**
Description of the procedures that will be implemented for the long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, its approximated end volume, the associated costs (if any), and how these will be covered.

1.6. Origin of Data

Most of the data will be generated by the project partners over the course of the project, together with the collaboration of external Stakeholders, except for certain data that will be retrieved from relevant databases. More details are available in paragraphs 1.7 and 1.8.

1.7. Types of data re-used within the project

The TRUSTyFOOD project will re-use data coming from other sources, specifically for WP2 and WP4 activities.

In the context of WP2, Task 2.1, the blockchain applications is thoroughly studied via documents at the public's disposal (online papers and online publications) and analyzed in detail to extract knowledge and insights.

In task 2.2, the beneficiaries map projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), other food-related sectors and the blockchain domain by conducting a thorough search in several databases. First, existing repositories that feature good practices throughout Europe are consulted; these include repositories that are global, European, national or regional in scope (CORDIS for European projects; BBI JU/CBE JU; ECSEL JU, PRIMA database; etc). Second, when looking for information about the experiments within these digital repositories, more web links could be found to other potentially interesting experiments, which are then further explored online.

In the context of WP4, Task 4.1 will search in several databases use cases that are relevant for climate change and agriculture/food and, in relation to GHG emission tracking, what other promising sustainability measures (apart from emission tracking) exist.

In Task 4.2, it is expected to use existing databases for carrying out an analysis of innovative business models specifically related to blockchain, as well as in Task 4.3 is the search for correlations between Blockchain Technology (BCT) applications and the transition to a sustainable, healthy and inclusive food system.

1.8. Types of data generated within the project

The TRUSTyFOOD project is expected to generate the following types of data:

- a. Database of pilots/ use cases of national, EU and International projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), other food related sectors and in the blockchain domain (WP2, T2.1/2.2)
- b. Data from the questionnaires submitted to *use cases' representatives* (WP2, T2.3 and 3.1)
- c. Data from *expert-interviews* (WP2, T2.3)
- d. Data from the questionnaires submitted to *non-use cases' representatives* (WP2, T2.3 and 3.1)
- e. Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry and first analysis of the agri-food sector digital maturity (WP2, T2.3)
- f. A database of stakeholders contacts coming from the database (WP2) and the *online consultation* (WP3, T3.1)
- g. Data collected inside *Clustering group* (WP3, T3.2)
- h. Data collected inside *Policy-makers meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- i. Data collected inside *Sectoral stakeholder meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- j. Data collected inside *Local Focus Group meetings* (WP3, T3.2)
- k. Data collected inside *Inter-sectoral stakeholder meetings (= Task Forces)* (WP3, T3.3)
- l. Data from *expert-interviews* (WP4, T4.1)
- m. Findings on BC applications impact in climate change adaptation or mitigation in agriculture (WP4, T4.1)
- n. New business models for BCT and impact on market (WP4, T4.2)
- o. Data for realising foresight scenarios for future applications of BCT (WP4, T4.3)
- p. Data from consensus building workshops (WP5, T5.2)
- q. Roadmap (WP5)
- r. White Papers (WP5)
- s. Policy Brief (WP1 and WP5)
- t. Collection of tools, guidelines, insights to animate an existing Platform of services for BCTs users which will survive after the project's end (WP5, T5.4)
- u. Scientific and technical papers, posters, videos, other publications (WP6)
- v. Data related to gender policy plan monitoring (WP1)

1.9. Data to be shared and not

Some of the above data will be shared with the scientific community in accordance with the open data sharing principles, some others will be maintained confidential. In detail:

- Data from category **(a)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D2.2) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project's website. Such data will be the starting point for identifying, for example, which BCT-applications may improve existing practices or create new disruptive innovation in climate change & agriculture/food as well as to identify the most interesting experiences functional to the selection of stakeholders' Board members.
- Data from category **(b)** will be shared with the scientific community as "aggregated data" and included in D2.1. Such data will be used inside the consortium for analysing in detail some use cases and identify patterns.
- Data from categories **(c)** will be treated in the following way: personal data will be managed in the full respect of GDPR principles and Ethics plan; personal opinions will

be collected and aggregated in general findings, and will be shared with the scientific community in anonymised form. Such data will be used inside the consortium for identifying patterns and for identifying the most interesting experiences functional to the selection of stakeholders' Board members.

- Data from category **(d)** will be shared with the scientific community as “aggregated data” and included in D2.1. Such data will be used inside the consortium for understanding current practices along the value chain.
- Data from category **(e)** will derive in part from (a), (b), (c) and (d) and in part by desk research and will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D2.1) saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project’s website. In addition, such data might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by TCA, INOV, INESC-ID and ENG. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Data from categories **(f)** will not be shared and will be managed in the full respect of GDPR principles and Ethics plan.
- Data from categories **(g) (h) (i) (j) (k)** will be shared partially in the full respect of GDPR principles and Ethics plan (humans and personal data), and partially with the scientific community, since they will feed the public Deliverables D3.2 and D3.3 which will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project’s website.
- Data from category **(l)** and **(m)** will be treated in the following way: personal data will be managed in the full respect of GDPR principles and Ethics plan; personal opinions, where the request for visibility does not arise directly with the interviewee and has not been previously agreed upon, will be collected and aggregated in general findings, and will be shared with the scientific community through the public Deliverable (D4.1) in anonymised form. Following the same principles, data from category **(l)** and **(m)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by Fraunhofer. Also in this case, an agreement with the interviewee will be necessary; where required, we will summarize/anonymize relevant results from the expert interviews. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Data from category **(n)** will be shared with the community, since it represents a public Deliverable (D4.2) that will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project’s website. In addition, data from category **(n)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications by UniKoblenz and the other involved partners. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community.
- Data from category **(o)** might be shared with the scientific community, following research publications. In case of accepted publications, selected datasets will be shared with the community for verification purposes.
- Data from categories **(p)** will be treated in the following way: personal data will be managed in the full respect of GDPR principles and Ethics plan; personal opinions will not be accessible as such but will be collected, aggregated in general findings, and will be shared with the scientific community in anonymised form for reinforcing the Roadmap contents.
- Data from categories **(q) (r)** and **(s)** will be shared with the scientific community, since they will feed the public Deliverables D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3, which will be saved in the CORDIS and uploaded on the project’s website. In addition, through the initiatives organised in Task 6.2, specific activities will be organised for a wide visibility of these documents to the community (scientific and end users)

- Data from category (t) will be shared with the community. We will not share technical details on the implementation of the ePlatform, but the contents included there will be available to the public at least for some basic functions and information
- Data from category (u) will be shared with the community.
- Data from category (v) will not be shared since it is confidential information.

1.10. Details on data generated

In the sections that follow, details on the data to be shared with the community are presented. Focus is put on:

- a) Dataset description
- b) Standards and metadata, where applicable
- c) Accessibility.

1.10.1. Database of pilots/ use cases

The data related to Database of pilots/ use cases of national, EU and International projects in the agri-food sector (including aquaculture and fisheries), in other food related sectors and in the blockchain domain are an output of WP2.

Such database is an ‘exhaustive’ report on blockchain applications collected via public documents at disposal, using several open databases/repositories throughout Europe, Middle-east and North-Africa.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D2.2)
2. Data for Task 4.1 activities
3. Possible data for scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available either in Microsoft Excel format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file. Data will be documented using a common template already used in similar studies (see FAO, 2021). The template used focuses on the following key details for each identified pilot /use case:

- [Company name]
- [Description of the application]
- [Website as reference]
- [Country of origin]
- [Industry / Sector]
- [Consortium type]
- [Contact referent]
- [Type of funding]
- [Main goals]
- [Permission model]

- [Cryptocurrency/Tokens]
- [Technology applied]
- [Single/ Multi organization]
- [Deployment]
- [Information sources]
- [Extra notes]

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results are documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or described by an additional document.

Metadata is made available in the form of a Dashboard available on the TRUSTyFOOD project website (<https://www.trustyfood.eu/framework-of-services/dashboard/>).

Accessibility:

As specified earlier and in Paragraph 1.9, the Database **is freely available** to the community. No embargo period is foreseen.

In addition, once a dataset is made available on the project repository (following a publication), it will freely be available to the community as well, in the way described in the appropriate section above. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.2. Data from the questionnaires/Interviews with use cases' representatives

In the context of Task 2.3 and 3.1, interviews/interactions through Questionnaires are foreseen to gather the needed information useful for analyzing the digital maturity and identifying emerging patterns (good and bad). Iteration focuses on their own experience in BCTs application developed in the specific Pilot context. The focus was given in the first section on technical details of the blockchain solution experimented with or collaborated to apply in a real-world case, and in the second one concerning the experience implementing the solution.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D2.1)
2. Possible data for scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

The survey is drafted on Microsoft Word format and then developed on Google Form document. Collected replies/data are downloaded to be available in the form of single completed questionnaires in .pdf format and a global visualization in Excel sheet.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results are documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory and in some cases described by an additional document.

Metadata is available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9 and above, questionnaires/Interviews minutes **are not directly accessible as such** to scientific community.

Unless differently agreed with the single interviewee, such kind of data will be processed and made available as anonymized and aggregate data; will be used for generating Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry (par. 1.10.4).

1.10.3. Data from the questionnaires submitted to non-use cases' representatives

In the context of Task 2.3 and 3.1, interactions through Questionnaires are foreseen to gather the needed information useful for analyzing the perception on the digital technology potential by the agri-food players. Iteration focuses on understanding perspectives and experiences with digital technology, and to understand how innovative technologies can fit into the broader objectives, challenges, and opportunities experienced by actors within the agri-food system.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D2.1)
2. Possible data for scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

The survey is drafted on Microsoft Word format and then developed on Google Form document. Collected replies/data are downloaded to be available in the form of single completed questionnaires in .pdf format and a global visualization in Excel sheet.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results are documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory and in some cases described by an additional document. Metadata is made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9 and above, questionnaires **are not directly accessible as such** to scientific community. Such kind of data will be processed and made available as anonymized and aggregate data; will be used for generating Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry (par. 1.10.4).

1.10.4. Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry

The data related to Findings on blockchain use for tackling problems in the agri-food industry are an output of WP2, coming from data mentioned in par. 1.10.1-2-3. Such data derive from an analysis and assessment done within the identified projects to evaluate working practices, implementation techniques, and remaining gaps.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D2.1)
2. Possible data for scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation is available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) and as a PDF file (for the community) under the form of Report.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results are documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or described by an additional document.

Metadata is made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, Deliverable 2.1 is made freely available to the community in the way described in the D6.1/D6.2 (i.e., once approved, public deliverables will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, all accepted public deliverables can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission). Additionally, some strategic partners are going to apply for a public peer-review article; in such case, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.5. A database of stakeholders contacts

The database will list different stakeholders with personal data such as:

- [name]
- [surname]
- [organization]
- [role]
- [email]

Information about tools and instruments:

Information are available in Microsoft Excel format.

Standards and metadata:

Not applicable

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the database will be an internal document, which **will not be directly accessible** to scientific community. Such data will be managed according to D1.5.

1.10.6. Data collected inside the discussion Groups (WGs, Focus Groups, TFs, etc)

Data that come from discussions with Stakeholders will be mainly generated as an output of WP3, in particular as an output of T3.2 and T3.3. Such data will include stakeholders' visions, experiences and opinions on BCT-related themes namely climate change mitigation, transparent and traceable supply chains and healthy, inclusive, and sustainable food systems.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for two public Deliverables (D3.2 and D3.3)
2. Preliminary data for Task 4.1 (preliminary results from the stakeholder engagement workshop on climate change, together with literature review and use case analysis, will

serve as a foundation to identify gaps and formulate the interview questions mentioned in par. 1.10.7)

3. Preliminary data for a Roadmap, White Papers and a Policy Brief (see par. 1.10.12-1.10.13-1.10.14)

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community) under the form of Report. ATLAS.ti will be used as a tool for data coding and visualisation.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research.

Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document.

Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section above, i.e.: once approved, public deliverables will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, all accepted public deliverables can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. In case of a public peer-review article, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.7. Data from expert-interviews

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of Task 4.1. Such data will include opinions from experts/stakeholders about the relationship of BCT-applications and climate change issues and will be strictly related to par. 1.10.8.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D4.1)
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in the Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, the Interviews minutes **will not be directly accessible as such** to scientific community. Unless differently agreed with the interviewees, data will be processed and made available as anonymized and aggregate data in D4.1 or in a peer review publication. In the

latest case, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.8. Data on BCT applications impact on climate change

Data on BCT applications impact on climate change will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.1. Such data came mainly from literature review, integrated by expert-interviews (see par. 1.10.7).

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D4.1)
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in the Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section above, i.e.: once approved, public deliverable will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, it can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. In case of a public peer-review article, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.9. Business Models

New business models will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.2. Such data will include the description of “new technologies” and their impact on the market and on business models in order to derive innovative business models for the incoming technologies such as BCT.

The following types of data will be produced:

3. Data for a public Deliverable (D4.2)
4. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Documentation will be available either in MS Word, MS Excel or PDF format.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will

be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section above i.e.: once approved, public deliverable will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, it can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. In case of a public peer-review article, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.10. Data for realizing foresight scenarios

Data for future scenarios will be mainly generated as an output of WP4, in particular as an output of task T4.3. Such data will include the description of “different possible futures”, from the more modest to the more revolutionary and what would need to happen for them to materialize, who will benefit, what is the potential impact in the environment, what are the societal challenges, what are the changes required in the current institutions.

The following types of data will be produced:

- Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available either in the Microsoft Word format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, data collected **might be shared** with the scientific community following **research publications**. In case of accepted publication, bibliographical data and abstract will be available immediately for consultation and open access.

1.10.11. Data from consensus building workshops

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP5, in particular as an output of consensus building workshops. Such data will include stakeholders' points of view on the current project's findings.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available in Microsoft Word format.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will

be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, data emerging **will not be directly accessible as such** to the scientific community, but will be integrated into the Roadmap (par. 1.10.12).

1.10.12. Roadmap

Data will be generated in WP1, WP3 and WP4, as well as T5.1. Such data will include recommendations for policy makers on which of the blockchain approaches are better suited to be applicable in agri-food and other food-sector domain, which business models are best for which type of entities, drawing conclusions on drivers and barriers (both technical and societal) to the further uptake of blockchain technologies and potential courses of action from the policy angle.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D5.2)
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available either in Microsoft Word (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section above i.e.: once approved, public deliverable will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, it can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. Specific dissemination channels will be activated as well.

1.10.13. White Papers

Data will be generated as an output of WP3 (T3.3) and WP5, in particular as an output of T5.3. Such data, in line with the Blockchain Strategy of the EC², will provide recommendations in terms of interoperability and standards, as well as blockchain skills development.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D5.1)
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/blockchain-strategy>

Information about tools and instruments:

Information will be available either in Microsoft Word format (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section above i.e.: once approved, public deliverable will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, it can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. Specific dissemination channels will be activated as well.

1.10.14. Policy Brief

Data will be generated in WP1, WP3 and WP4, as well as T5.1. Such data will include information to prepare a concise summary that can help readers understand and likely make decisions concerning government policies. A policy brief presents a concise summary of information that can help readers understand, and likely make decisions about, government policies.

The following types of data will be produced:

1. Data for a public Deliverable (D5.3)
2. Possible data used in scientific and technical publications

Information about tools and instruments:

Information regarding the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word (for internal use only) or as a PDF file (for the community).

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, generated data **will freely be available** to the community in the way described in the appropriate section above i.e.: once approved, public deliverable will be uploaded on the project website and on TRUSTyFOOD community on Zenodo. In addition, it can be found from the project's CORDIS page provided by the European Commission. Specific dissemination channels will be activated as well.

1.10.15. Collection of tools, guidelines, insights to animate an existing Platform of services

Data will be generated as an output of task T5.3. Such data will originate from an online collaboration space providing support to Community members - e.g., idea generation, hackathons, awards and challenges, including discussion fora, wikis and blogs.

Information will be available online on the Platform, either as HTML pages or as downloadable documents in the MS Word, MS Excel or PDF format. Deliverable 5.4 will provide instructions.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, we will not share technical details on the implementation of the Platform, but **the contents included there will be available to the public.**

1.10.16. Scientific and technical papers, posters, videos, other publications

Data from this category are intended for sharing with the research community or even the general public. All scientific publications will adhere to the green or golden “open access” model. Non-scientific publications will be freely distributed to all interested party.

Data collected is related to the developments of T6.1, which runs throughout the project. Information on the planned publications is included in the Communication and Dissemination Plan_v1, 2 and 3, which is regularly updated.

Publications will be shared in the form of pdf, video or photo files. At the moment, it is not possible to estimate the file size.

The possible use or re-use by the scientific community is provided by adhering to terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement, as well as to the terms of the publisher.

Information about tools and instruments: It is not foreseen the need to use specialised tools. Any datasets used in scientific papers will also be accessible through the same location.

Accessibility: Once a publication is made available on the project repository, it will freely be available to the community, in the way described in the appropriate section above. No embargo period is foreseen.

1.10.17. Data from gender policy plan monitoring

Data will be mainly generated as an output of WP1, in particular as an output of T1.2. Such data will include:

- Awareness and knowledge of the project Gender Policy Plan
- Awareness and knowledge of the EU Gender Equality Strategy
- Awareness and knowledge of gender-sensitive communication guidelines
- Gender-equal working environment
- Negative discrimination
- Policies, Standards, Procedures, and Guidelines
- Knowledge of how to report gender-related issues

For more details, see D1.1.

Information about tools and instruments:

Information about the survey will be available either in Microsoft Word/ Excel format or as a PDF file.

Standards and metadata:

To guarantee a high academic standard, results will be documented considering the typical nomenclature of the particular field of research. Measured data are either self-explanatory or will be prepared or described by an additional document. Metadata will be made available for each document or dataset.

Accessibility:

As specified in Paragraph 1.9, such data **will not be directly accessible** to the scientific community.

2. FAIR data

The European Commission has highlighted the importance of making the data produced by European-funded projects **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)**, with a view to ensuring its sound management, as well as boosting the dissemination of relevant information and the easy exchange of data within the EU state members. Thus, EU's FAIR data approach implements standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data.

The following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of TRUSTyFOOD with respect to making data findable, accessible and interoperable, as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

1.11. Making data findable and accessible

All sharable data will be published and hosted as per individual availability on the online long term repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/trustyfood/?page=1&size=20>

The screenshot displays the Zenodo website interface. At the top, the Zenodo logo is on the left, followed by a search bar and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. On the right, there is a user profile dropdown for 'info@trustyfood.eu'. Below the navigation bar, the page title 'TRUSTyFOOD' is centered. Underneath, there is a 'Recent uploads' section with a search bar containing 'TRUSTyFOOD' and a 'More' button. To the right, a 'New upload' button is visible above a community card for 'TRUSTyFOOD'. The community card includes the TRUSTyFOOD logo and the following metadata: 'Curated by: TRUSTyFOOD', 'Curation policy: Not specified', 'Created: December 9, 2022', and 'Harvesting API: OAI-PMH Interface'.

Partners will be instructed to upload datasets, publications, or deliverables to the repository.

The consortium will make sure that available data will be easily recoverable by any interested party. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application and the search function on the Zenodo website.

The **Zenodo** community is already acting as a one-stop-shop for data generated by EU projects and, thus, makes it easier for the data to be discovered by interested parties.

The data will be formatted as per the description of each section provided previously in this document and will be presented for access along with the necessary links to download the appropriate software tools, if necessary.

The pages will be available in the public domain, enriched with the necessary metadata and will be open to web crawlers for search engine listing, so they will be available to the public through standard web searches.

Despite the publicly available pages, the downloadable data will be presented along with possible restrictions provided in each previously described section.

Downloadable formats will be:

1. PNG, BMP, TIFF and JPEG file formats
2. ZIP and other public domain compressed archives
3. PDF formatted documents
4. WMV, MP4 or AVI formats for possible videos

All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including the Grant Number and our Project Acronym. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements (if there is no DOI from a publisher). An automatic indexing in OpenAIRE will occur as well.

Using a naming convention in a structured way makes it easier for outsiders to find results.

Zenodo will keep the data available for the lifetime of the repository, at the moment that is estimated to be at least 20 years.

Links to some of the data, especially in terms of publications, posters, videos etc. will also be directly available on the **project website**: www.trustyfood.eu. In terms of Deliverables, 15 are expected to be published and made fully accessible to the public.

In addition, Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in **CORDIS project's page** and will remain online post-project's end.

1.12. Making data interoperable

The data formats must all be non-proprietary data formats to ensure interoperability (MS Office), or in common formats that are used by people skilled in the field.

The consortium will make sure that TRUSTyFOOD data includes qualified references to other data (e.g. other data or datasets from previous research).

1.13. Data re-use

In line with the above-mentioned European Commission vision (par. 1.2), the data generated along the TRUSTyFOOD project lifespan that can be shared will be made available as Open access research data; this refers to the right to access and re-use research data. Openly accessible

research data can be accessed, mined, exploited, reproduced and disseminated free of charge for the User.

1.14. Increase data re-use

To facilitate data re-use, in case of uncertain interpretation of terms used, a ‘glossary’ will be provided in combination with datasets.

All the data categorized as “made freely available in the public domain” in paragraph 1.10 are intended to permit the widest re-use possible. Such data produced in the project are thought to be useable by third parties along the project’s lifespan and, in particular, after the end of the project. The main target audience is represented by policy-makers, the scientific community interested in BCTs and end users (farmers, food producers, and all the other players in the food system).

3. Other research outputs

Inside TRUSTyFOOD, apart from data, Engineering Ingegneria Informatica will re-use a Platform already developed in a previously funded project.

The beneficiary, in line with the FAIR principles, will not share technical details on the implementation of the ePlatform, but the contents included there will be available to the public at least for some basic functions and information.

4. Allocation of resources

4.1. Estimated costs of making data FAIR

Costs emerging from the FAIR data management process are integrated within the budget of TRUSTyFOOD.

In this respect:

- All publications related to the research conducted during the project will be submitted to scientific journals that comply with an open-access policy, and the fees will be covered by the budget allocated by the Grant;
- Zenodo is offered at no cost. TCA has created and curates the community (through the email info@trustyfood.eu), and new data might be added even after the project concludes;
- Regarding the TRUSTyFOOD project website, ownership and payments are under TCA’s responsibility. The company has planned to maintain the website for a period of at least three (3) years after the completion of the project (and most probably beyond that). The related cost is relatively small per year and will be covered by the company’s own funds.

4.2. Data management responsibilities

Efficient, proper and safe processing of the collected/generated data throughout TRUSTyFOOD involves the implementation of specific data management roles within the project’s data management methodology and procedures. These responsibilities are outlined in this section.

□ **Project Coordinator (PCO):** The PCO, TCA, is responsible for overall data management in the framework of TRUSTyFOOD, including the elaboration of the DMP. At the same time, the PCO is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant

activities of the project. Finally, the PCO coordinates with Work Package and Task Leaders to determine whether and how the data produced/used by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance.

□ **Work Package Leaders (WPLs):** The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. They align with the PCO and the respective Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

□ **Task Leaders (TLs):** The TLs act as data controllers of the data collected/generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership, determining the purposes and means of processing this data as well as safeguarding its appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data produced/used through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymization techniques, the creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

5. Data security

Documents, including personal data (e.g. questionnaires, databases), will not be publicly accessible, but will remain stored in the servers of each project's partner. Each project partner will manage such data according to the internal GDPR rules in place (see more in D1.5).

In case of transfer of sensitive data from one partner to another, trusted repositories will be selected. In particular, the consortium agreed on using **Freedcamp** management platform, which provides an online collaboration tool that allows multiple users to coordinate on projects, tasks and other endeavors. A dedicated TRUSTyFOOD Folder has been created on this platform. The management of Freedcamp related to the project is under the responsibility of the coordinator (TCA).

Freedcamp makes commercially reasonable efforts to ensure that all facilities used to store and process User Data meet a high standard for security. In good faith, it exercises due diligence using reasonable business practices for IT security to ensure that systems are operated and maintained in a secure manner, and that management, operational and technical controls are employed to ensure the security of systems and data. Recognizing the changing nature of the Web, Freedcamp will continuously work with users to ensure that its Site and Services meet users' requirements for the security of systems and data.

Freedcamp has the following standard security settings:

- **Access level:** Restricted to persons (project members only) at the invitation of the project's coordinator. Further access restrictions on specific folders are enabled and Freedcamp is committed to ensuring that Data is not seen by anyone who should not have access to it.
- **Encryption:** The Freedcamp services support the latest recommended secure cipher suites and protocols to encrypt all traffic in transit and rest. We monitor the changing cryptographic landscape closely and work promptly to upgrade the service to respond to new cryptographic weaknesses as they are discovered and implement best practices as they evolve.

- Network protection: In addition to sophisticated system monitoring and logging, we are running Security-Enhanced Linux (SELinux) in enforcing mode. Firewalls are configured according to industry best practices and unnecessary ports are blocked by configuration with AWS Security Groups.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevent and/or register possible manipulation of data.

The type and number of tools and services will depend on which Paid Plan User. Freedcamp's Free plan is provided at zero cost to all Users; its essential features are considered enough for TRUSTyFOOD data management. No resources are thus expected to be spent for storage, even if the repository allows for upgrades. In the case of need, TCA is in charge of sustaining such kind of expenses.

For data shared, CERN maintains a very strict security policy around data stored on its servers Zenodo that needs to stay confidential. For public data, security can be less strict. For the preservation of the public files, Zenodo has: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/>

6. Ethics

In the case of data sharing, informed consent and long-term preservation will be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data. More details in D1.5.